

Exploring Microtonal Harmony

with Web Audio and Web MIDI

David Paulick
Les Lilas, France
ftdmp@orange.fr

ABSTRACT

One aspect of musical practise that can be greatly facilitated by Web Audio and Web MIDI technologies is microtonality - tunings and temperaments that use more than twelve tones to the octave. The possibility of creating new interfaces, instruments, and tutorial materials is simplified by the combined visual and audio capabilities of JavaScript. Web Audio applications can be made inexpensively available and immediately explorable by web users.

With that in mind, I have used Web MIDI and Web Audio to create a simple instrument that enables users to experience, explore, and work with microtonality - specifically with the system of Just Intonation. The application is a playable Tonality Diamond and can be used effectively in combination with readily available MIDI controller hardware. It is available at tonalitydiamond.com. In this talk I will present the basic concepts behind the project with audio examples.

1. Advantages of Working with the Harmonic Series

Over the last 200 years, the system of twelve-tone equal temperament, or 12-TET, has been ubiquitous in western music and beyond. The twelve keys of the piano keyboard have remained largely unquestioned as the basis of modern musical theory and practice. The adoption of this standard has enabled many important musical developments - particularly by facilitating the seamless modulation between different musical keys. In 12-TET, the tuning of all intervals except the octave is altered, sometimes quite drastically, so that they can be used in several senses. This compromise has hindered the expansion of harmony as a complex system based on natural and mathematical principles. As several comparatively consonant tones are unavailable to musicians in this system, the natural harmonic spectrum provides a much greater sonic pallet.

There are many diverse approaches to increasing musical resources through microtonality, including other equal divisions of the octave. This talk is primarily concerned with frequency ratios derived from the harmonic series of naturally occurring overtones

- as well as their reciprocals, sometimes called the subharmonic series, and the relationships between them. This is the basis of Just Intonation a system in which small number ratios are used to define musical intervals, and which can include tones not approximated in 12-TET. Ratios are used to represent relationships between tones. $5/4$, for example, is a pitch that is $5/4$ times faster than $1/1$, the fundamental frequency. A tempered version of $5/4$, 13.6 per cent of a semitone sharp, is the 12-TET major third, E in the key of C, or B in the key of G.

2. Web Audio and Frequency Ratios

While MIDI based instruments and most DAWs are somewhat restricted by the MIDI protocol, only beginning to be more flexible since the recent advent of MPE, MIDI Polyphonic Expression, working in JavaScript code allows the composer/ developer to work directly with ratios, and the laborious process of converting frequencies to MIDI pitch bend numbers can be avoided. An oscillator's frequency can be set to a ratio multiplied by a fundamental frequency in hertz and then heard as audio.

```
const key = 392;
```

```
oscillator.frequency.setValueatTime(0, 7/6 * key);
```

A scale or musical sequence of any length can be represented by an array of ratios and used accordingly.

```
const scale =[1/1,9/8,5/4,11/8,3/2,13/8,7/4,15/8];
```

Some useful terminology:

Cent is a measurement devised by Alexander J Ellis, for determining the distance of a musical ratio from the nearest 12-TET "semitone". While extremely useful for communicating with musicians with knowledge of 12-TET, it can be limiting to think of certain intervals as variations or detunings of commonly used 12-TET counterparts.

Example for converting a ratio to cent value:

```
const ratioToCent = (ratio) => 1200*(Math.log( ratio )/  
Math.log(2));
```

Octave Reduction means bringing a ratio within the range of a single octave, between $1/1$ and $2/1$. For instance the third harmonic $3/1$ could be octave reduced to $3/2$ by increasing the denominator by a power of two. $3/1$, $3/2$, $3/4$, and $3/8$ will all be heard as the same pitch in a different octave, as will its reciprocal, the third subharmonic, $1/3$, $2/3$, $4/3$, $8/3$, $16/3$.

In Just Intonation theory, **Limits** are all ratios within an octave using prime numbers not exceeding a certain number. As an example, the five limit includes the intervals:

$1/1$, $6/5$, $5/4$, $4/3$, $3/2$, $8/5$, $5/3$, $2/1$.

3. Tonality Diamonds

The Tonality Diamond was used by instrument builder, composer and microtonal theorist Harry Partch to show the "at least dual identity" of musical ratios and possibilities for chord construction within a Just Intonation limit. The diamond had previously been presented in the research of the Mexican composer and theorist Augusto Novaro and that of the American psychologist Max Meyer.

Below is the five limit diamond - With the major triad $1/1$, $5/4$, $3/2$ ascending and the minor triad $1/1$, $8/5$, $4/3$ descending, with the $1/1$ representing the "perfect fifth" of the chord. Five limit ratios were the foundation of the post Renaissance tonal system, with the introduction of major and minor chords.

Five Limit Tonality Diamond

In the Tonality Diamonds presented here, what Partch calls Otonalities, intervals derived from the harmonic series, are displayed from left to right. Utonalities, from the subharmonic series, are displayed from right to left. The $1/1$ recurs in the middle showing its multiple identities. I have kept Partch's convention of labelling the intervals with their octave reduced form, rather than the actual frequency.

Seven Limit Tonality Diamond

The seven limit diamond, first presented by Max Meyer in *The Musician's Arithmetic*, introduces ratios of seven, related to the seventh harmonic. The $7/4$ is a very audible 21.2 cent flatter than the flat seventh in 12-TET. By displaying the diamond without octave reduction we can see the relationship between Just Intonation and the harmonic series. Ascending to the right are the first seven odd harmonics, descending left the first seven odd subharmonics. They are combined to create more intervals. When the intervals are octave reduced they form chords resulting in a series of "dominant" and minor seventh chords.

Seven Limit Tonality Diamond without octave reduction

With each increase in limit more musical possibilities are found. The $11/8$ is 48.7 cent flatter than a fifth in 12-TET, close to a quarter tone. The eleven limit was the basis of the 43 tone scale used by Harry Partch. His 29 tone diamond marimba is a playable version of the eleven limit Tonality Diamond.

Making the intervals audible makes it much easier to perceive the increased musical possibilities. The simple Web Audio instrument presented here makes the Tonality Diamonds playable for the purpose of study, composition or performance. A looping function is available to create more complex musical structures. Using Web MIDI, a Novation Launchpad or another suitably mapped MIDI controller can be used to play the instrument. The eight by eight grid of the Launchpad is ideal for the "15 limit" diamond, but also usable for extended versions of lower limit diamonds.

Fifteen is not technically a limit as it is not a prime number, but rather a product of 3 and 5, yet it increases musical possibilities by bringing in ratios of both 13 and 15. The $13/8$ is 40.53 cent sharper than a minor sixth, and therefore offers a flavour not found in 12-TET. More familiar is $15/8$: the octave reduced fifteenth harmonic, 11.7 cents flatter than the 12-TET major seventh - also the just major third ($5/4$) of the perfect fifth ($3/2$) - known to most musicians through the use of extended major chords built on thirds (5 limit ratios).

4. Higher Harmonics

A number of composers have experimented with more complex intervals and higher harmonics. La Monte Young in his sine-tone installations has gone as far as the 2304th harmonic and perhaps

further. Ben Johnston's 7th string quartet uses more than 176 Just Intonation pitches. Johnny Reinhard, organiser of the American Festival of Microtonal Music and the online Microtonal University, has worked extensively with 128, a tuning based on the eighth octave of the harmonic series, avoiding the lower harmonics which strongly define the tonality. Zheanna Eroze's theory of primodality, creating modes out of subsections of the harmonic series, is a notably accessible approach. For the purpose of experimenting with intervals derived from higher harmonics, I've adapted the 8 by 8 playable diamond to prime numbers greater than 13, 17 to 41, but other selective higher harmonic scales could also be used. By placing them on the diamond the same possibilities for inversion and chord building are available as with the diamonds based on lower harmonics.

5. Future possibilities

While the implementation of microtonal capabilities is picking up speed, there is still a need for readily available tools and tutorials for the interested electronic musician. Traditional DAWs are still very much designed for a 12-TET approach and the traditional seven white and five black key Halberstadt keyboard layout. With Web Audio there is the opportunity to open microtonality to broader audiences who might not have affordable access to proprietary music software. With Web MIDI, MIDI controllers can be turned into physically playable musical instruments accompanied by onscreen visual reinforcement. Some applications that could be developed include microtonal sequencers, mini DAWs as compositional aids, piano roll editors, pitch detectors, tuners, and visualisers. Integration with MPE or the MIDI Tuning Standard, the possibility of outputting MIDI files with pitch bend numbers, would also facilitate communication with other electronic music technologies, placing Web Audio applications as essential elements of the electronic toolkit for microtonal musicians.

Web Audio developers could play a major part in bringing about a deeper understanding of harmony and intonation by putting together simple, easily accessible applications with strong visual and audio interconnectivity. The web could provide a gentle gateway for the adventurous electronic musician, contributing to the expansion of musical vocabulary in the coming years.

Higher Prime Tonicity Diamond

6. References

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